

Global Perspectives in Multidisciplinary Research

The Influence of Acceptance of ZISWAF (Zakat, Infaq, Alms and Waqf), FDR (Financing to Deposit Ratio) and CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio) on Wadiah Current Savings with Firm Size as a Moderation Variable in Islamic Banking in Indonesia Period of 2018-2023

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Abstract: This research aims to determine, analyze and test the influence of ZISWAF (Zakat, Infaq, Alms and Waqf), FDR (Financing to Deposit Ratio) and CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio) funds on Wadiah Current Account Savings with firm size as a moderating variable in Islamic banking context. The research sample consists of sharia banking financial data from the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, with a total sample of 5 companies during the period 2018.Q1 to 2023.Q3. The data analysis technique used is Panel Data Regression Analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with the Eviews 12 application. The data analysis method used is a statistical method that is suitable for answering this research question. The research results show that receipt of ZISWAF, FDR and CAR funds have a significant influence on Wadiah Giro Savings in sharia banking. Apart from that, firm size also moderates the relationship between ZISWAF, FDR and CAR fund receipts and Wadiah Giro Savings. These results show the importance of managing ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds in improving the financial performance of sharia banking and reducing the risk of Wadiah Current Account Deposits. In future research, it is hoped that other variables will be used as moderating variables and samples of companies from other sectors will be used so that the research results can also represent other business sectors.

Keywords: ZISWAF Fund, FDR, CAR, Wadiah Giro Savings, Firm Size

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has faced economic conditions between economic growth and income distribution. In Islam, there are separate means to solve the problem of equal distribution of income which are known as Zakat, Infaq, Sadaqah and Waqf or commonly called ZISWAF (Sardiana & Zulfison, 2016).

ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds (Zakat, Infaq, Shodaqah and Waqf) are an instrument for wealth distribution in the Islamic economic system. These four instruments are only zakat, which is legally obligatory for every Muslim, but the other three are a means of giving alms to other Muslims. ZISWAF has two meanings: Efforts to carry out the commands of God Almighty, and efforts to fulfill social responsibilities (Masharif, 2017)

The potential for raising ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds in Indonesia cannot be underestimated. In the last 10 years, the emergence of ZISWAF management

and distribution institutions in Indonesia has almost become a kind of new business competition.(Sugita et al., 2020).

Economic development activities cannot be separated from the banking sector, because the banking industry plays an important role in economic growth and stability. According to Law Number 10 of 1998 concerning banking, a bank is a business entity that collects funds from the public in the form of savings and distributes them to the public in the form of credit or other forms to improve the standard of living of many people.(Muliawati & Khoiruddin, 2014).

Currently, banking growth in Indonesia is experiencing rapid progress. This happens to Conventional Banks and Sharia Banks. In Islamic banks themselves, there is profitability, which means a bank's ability to earn profits expressed as a percentage. One of the factors that can influence profitability is the Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR). The Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR) is the amount of funding issued by a sharia bank to support investments that have been planned for a certain time from the results of raising third party funds.(Hanafia & Karim, 2020).

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is the ratio of the minimum capital requirement (KPM) that banks must fulfill. This capital includes paid-in capital and capital deposit funds, general reserves, other reserves, remaining profits from last year and the current year. The higher the CAR value, the stronger the bank's ability to bear the risk of any credit and risky productive assets. (Yanuartha, 2019)CAR is a financial indicator related to a bank's capital. If the bank's capital can cover unavoidable losses, then the management of all its activities will run effectively, including the bank's assets.(Rositasari & Dailibas, 2022).

In practice, sharia banks provide current and savings deposit services based on the principle/contract of wadi'ah yad dhamanah. With this principle, banks as depositors are obliged to guarantee repayment of the nominal value of wadi'ah deposits. These funds can be used by the bank for commercial activities. Deposit owners can withdraw their deposits at any time, either in part or in whole. Thus, in this checking and savings product, both the bank and the customer benefit. However, Sharia Banks may not state or promise any rewards or benefits to wadi'ah account holders, and vice versa, account holders may not expect or ask for rewards or benefits on wadi'ah accounts. Any reward or profit promised can be considered usury. However, banks, of their own free will, can provide rewards in the form of bonuses (grants) to fund owners (wadi'ah account holders).(Najib, 2017).

Firm size (company size) is one of the factors that can increase profitability. The larger the firm size, the higher the costs incurred, which can reduce profitability. Large companies tend to have a larger scale and greater economic freedom compared to small companies, so it will be easier to borrow capital which will ultimately increase the company's profitability.(Sari & Budiasih, 2014).

This research aims to analyze the effect of receiving ZISWAF, FDR and Wadiah Savings funds on Wadiah Current Account Savings with Sharia Banking Firm Size.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is a quantitative method. The data used in this research is secondary data originating from various literature such as books, journals and articles to access the latest data and information. The population used is banking financial reports in 2018.Q1–2023.Q3 with a sampling technique using purposive sampling

technique. The sample used was 5 banking company financial reports in 2018q1.Q1–2023.Q3, so the total sample was 115 financial reports in 2018-2023.

The data analysis methods used in this research are the Panel Data Regression Model and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). The interaction test or often called Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) uses an analytical approach that maintains sample integrity and provides a basis for providing the influence of moderator variables (Ghozali, 2018). The following is the model equation in panel data regression analysis:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Wadiah Giro Savings

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

X2 = FDR

X3 = CAR

e_i = Error

Hypothesis testing in this study uses regression analysis with the moderating variable Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA), the regression equation contains elements of interaction with the following equation formula:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4Z + \beta_5X_1*Z + \beta_6X_2*Z + \beta_7X_3*Z + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Wadiah Giro Savings

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

X2 = FDR

X3 = CAR

Z = Firm Size

X1*Z = Interaction of the influence of receiving ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds with moderation of firm size

X2*Z = Interaction of the influence of FDR with firm size moderation

X3*Z = Interaction of CAR influence with firm size moderation

e_i = Error

DISCUSSION

Research result

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	X1	X2	X3	y	z
Mean	25082.01	78.28383	26.00174	3397786.	13.39930
Maximum	669879.0	118.9400	149.6800	27797852	17.14000
Minimum	0.000000	38.33000	10.16000	12930.00	9.470000
Std. Dev.	87500.44	17.23037	18.96131	6651346.	1.974903

Observations	115	115	115	115	115
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Source: Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 1, it can be seen that the number of research samples on the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds are 115 samples from Financial Sector Companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) 2018-2023. In the ZISWAF fund receipt variable (X1) based on the results of descriptive statistics in Table 1, it can be seen that the Ziswaf fund receipt variable has an average value 25082.01, maximum value 669879.0, minimum value 0.000000, and standard deviation 87500.44.

For the FDR variable (X2), based on the results of the descriptive statistics in Table 1, it can be seen that the FDR variable has an average value of 78.28383, a maximum value of 118.9400, a minimum value of 38.33000, and a standard deviation of 17.23037.

In the CAR variable (X3), based on the results of the descriptive statistics in Table 1, it can be seen that the net profit/loss variable has an average value of 26.00174, a maximum value of 149.6800, a minimum value of 10.16000, and a standard deviation of 18.96131.

In the firm size (Z) variable, based on the results of descriptive statistics in Table 1, it can be seen that the profitability variable calculated using the Return on Assets formula has an average value of 13.39930, a maximum value of 17.14000, a minimum value of 9.470000, and a standard deviation of 1.97490.

In the Wadiah Current Account Savings (Y) variable, based on the descriptive statistics results contained in Table 1, it can be seen that the Wadiah Current Account Savings variable has an average value of 3397786, maximum value 17.14000, minimum value 9.470000, and standard deviation 1.974903.

Selection of Panel Data Regression Models

Selection of a panel data regression model is an analysis stage to determine the best method between Common Effect, Fixed Effect or Random Effect

Test Chow

This test is used to find out the best model between the Common Effect Model (CEM) and Fixed Effect Model (FEM), and Random Effect Model (REM).

Source:

Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Table 2. Chow Test Results

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	20.367	(4,106)	0.000
Chi-square section	65.571	3	0.000

Based on table 2, the Chow test results show that the Chi-squer cross-section probability value is 0.0000 <0.05. So it can be said that in this test, the best model to use is the fixed effect model (FEM).

Hausman test

The Hausman test aims to select the best

model between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Random Effect Model (REM).

Table 3. Hausman Test Results

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	df	Prob.
Random section	81.4711	39	0.0000

Source:

Eviews (Data processed by the author)

From table 3 above, it can be seen that the results of the Hausman test show a probability value of $0.000 < 0.05$. So it can be said that in this test, the best model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

Table 4. Normality Test

Source:

Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on Figure 4 above, it shows that the probability value is 0.000000, which means the probability value is below 0.05 ($0.000000 < 0.05$). So it can be concluded that the data in the research is not distributed normal.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

Source:

Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 5, the results of the multicollinearity test can be seen if the correlation values between the independent variables are all

	X1	X2	X3
X1	1	0.0037259365	0.0804474898
X2	0.0037259365	1	0.0294322
X3	0.0804474898	0.0294322	1

below 0.85. This means that if the research data does not contain multicollinearity between independent variables

	00294322		0.0371730363
	-	-	4317266
	0.0804474898	0.0371730363	
X3	5749898	4317266	1

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
	-	-	-	-
C	996854.677608	14.7113	14.7113	0.0000
X1	11.4565411034	2.78725	2.78725	0.0063
	-	-	-	-
X2	893.738399198	2.23883	2.23883	0.0272
X3	90.1275220339	0.40904	0.40904	0.6833
Z	106377.640396	16.6111	16.6111	0.0000

Source:

Eviews (Data processed by the author)
Based on table 6, the results of the heteroscedasticity test show that the resulting probability value is above 0.05. A regression model is said to be free from heteroscedasticity if it has a probability value above 0.05. So it can be concluded that in the regression model used in this research there is no heteroscedasticity.

Panel Data Regression Analysis

The following is a panel data regression analysis using the best model, namely the Fixed Effect Model regression :

Table 7. Fixed Effect Panel Data Regression Analysis

Source:

Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Regression Analysis (MRA)

Moderating variables can be interpreted as variables that can strengthen or weaken the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The following are the test results from the moderation analysis:

Table 8. Moderation Regression Analysis Test

Source:

Eviews (Data processed by the author)

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
	-	-	-	-
C	49059580	5869415.83585130	8.3585130	0.0000
X1	22.2939	3.67146760722300	6.04371	0.0000
X2	21367.1	19559.6010924120	1.09241	0.2771
X3	12828.9	14262.8608994620	0.8994620	0.3704

Variables Coeffici Std. t- Prob.

Statistical Test	ent	Error	Statistics
T test			
T test, to test whether partially the dependent variable has a significant effect on the independent variable. Apart from that, it is also used to determine whether the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable is tested at a significant level of 0.05 or with a confidence level of 95% and an error rate of 5%.			
	548096.		
C	4	147887910.037062	0.9705
	-		
	1805.01		-
X1	9	426.6667	4.230513
	-		0.0000
	374183.		-
X2	9	177033.5	2.113633
	200617.		0.0369
X3	4	146851.4	1.366125
	108.656		0.1748
Z	0	25.18349	4.314571
	28955.5		0.0000
X2Z	9	13479.87	2.148061
	-		0.0340
	15740.4		-
X3Z	2	14048.60	1.120426
			0.2650

Table 9. T Test Results

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	54809	1478870.0370	0.970	0.970
	6.4	91	62	5
	-		-	
X1	1805.0	426.66	4.2305	0.000
	19	67	13	0
	-		-	
X2	37418	177033	2.1136	0.036
	3.9	.5	33	9
	20061	146851	1.3661	0.174
X3	7.4	.4	25	8
	108.65	25.183	4.3145	0.000
X1Z	60	49	71	0
	28955.	13479.	2.1480	0.034
X2Z	59	87	61	0
	-		-	
	15740.	14048.	1.1204	0.265
X3Z	42	60	26	0

Source:
 Eviews (Data processed by the author)
 Based on the t test (partial) that the author has carried out in this research, it can be seen that the results obtained from the t test are as follows:
 Hypothesis 1 (H1): Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has an influence on Wadiah Current Account Savings. With a coefficient value of -1805.019 and a probability

value of 0.000, which means it is smaller than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that acceptance and ZISWAF have an influence on FDR in financial sector companies for the 2018-2023 period.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): FDR has an influence on Wadiah Current Account Savings. With a coefficient value of -374183.9 and a probability value of 0.0369, which means it is smaller than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that FDR has an influence on Wadiah Giro Savings in financial sector companies for the 2018-2023 period.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): CAR has an influence on Wadiah Current Account Savings. With a coefficient value of 200617.4 and a probability value of 0.1748, which means it is smaller than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that CAR has an influence on Wadiah Current Account Savings in financial sector companies for the 2018-2023 period.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds

influences Wadiah Current Account Savings, moderated by firm size. With a coefficient value of 108.6560 and a probability value of 0.0000, which means it is greater than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that the firm size is unable to receive ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds for Wadiah Giro Savings in financial sector companies for the 2018-2023 period.

Mean			
dependent var	339778	Adjusted squared	R-0.792243

Hypothesis 5 (H5): FDR's effect on Wadiah Current Account Savings is moderated by firm size. With a coefficient value of 28955.59 and a probability value of 0.0340, which means it is greater than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that firm size is unable to moderate the FDR of Wadiah Current Account Deposits in financial sector companies for the 2018-2023 period.

Hypothesis 6(H5): CAR's effect on Wadiah Current Account Savings is moderated by firm size. With a coefficient value of -15740.42 and a probability value of 0.2650, which means it is greater than the significant value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that firm size is unable to moderate the CAR of Wadiah Current Account Deposits in financial sector companies for the 2018-2023 period.

F test

The F test is used to test whether the independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on the dependent variable. The following are the results of the F test:

Table 10. F Test Results

Durbin-Watson stat	1.405593	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000
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Source:

Eviews (Data processed by the author)

The F test in this study uses a significance value of 0.05 or 5% with the criterion that if the F significance value is <0.05 then the regression coefficient is appropriate to use. The F test results in table 11 above show a significance value of F of 0.000000, this value is smaller than the significance value of 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that institutional ownership and capital structure simultaneously have an influence on company value.

Determiner coefficient test

The Determination Coefficient is used to show how much the independent variable contributes to the regression model in explaining variations in the dependent variable.

Based on table 11, the results of the panel data regression test on company value as the dependent variable, shows that the Adjusted R2 value is 0.792243. This can be interpreted as meaning that 79.322% of the Wadiah Giro Savings variable can be

explained by the receipt of ZISWAF, FDR and CAR funds. Meanwhile, the rest can be explained by other variables outside the regression model.

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on Wadiah Current Account Savings

The influence of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on Wadi'ah Giro savings is a complex problem with various factors playing a role. (Muzakir & Dharma (2020a)). Muzakir (2020) found that Wadi'ah Giro and Wadi'ah Savings have a significant influence on net profit at PT. BRI Syariah Bank. This shows that ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds which are often used for Wadiah Giro savings can have a positive influence on the financial performance of sharia banks. However, Indahsari (2014, 2016) highlighted the importance of trust in amil institutions which play an important role in managing ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds. This trust is very important for the effectiveness of ZISWAF fund distribution, which in turn can have an impact on the availability of funds for Wadiah Giro savings. Therefore, although ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds can have a positive influence on Wadiah Giro savings, this depends on factors such as the financial performance of Islamic banks and trust in amil institutions.

The Influence of FDR on Wadiah Current Account Savings

The influence of FDR on Wadiah Giro savings can be seen in several studies. Muzakir et al., (2020a) and Jakir (2018) both found that Wadi'ah Giro and Wadi'ah Savings had a significant influence on net profit at PT. BRI Syariah Bank. Falahuddin et al., (2021) further supports this by showing that Wadiah Savings has a positive and significant influence on Wadiah Bonuses at PT. Bank Muamalat Indonesia. Jannah (2019) also highlights the role of profit sharing, service and religion in influencing customers' interest in wadi'ah savings. These results show that FDR, especially in the form of Giro Wadiah savings, plays an important role in the financial performance and interest of sharia bank customers.

The Effect of CAR on Wadiah Current Account Savings

Rahman & Baihaqi (2022) found that profit sharing funds, murabahah, and wadiah savings have a significant positive effect on wadiah bonuses in Islamic banks. This shows that the use of sharia financial instruments, including wadiah giro savings, can affect the bonuses customers receive. However, further research is needed to specifically explore the impact of wadiah giro savings on these bonuses. CAR (Capital Adequacy Ratio) is a capital adequacy ratio that shows a bank's ability to fulfill its obligations to customers, including wadiah demand deposits.

The influence of ZISWAF Fund Receipts on Wadiah Current Account Savings with firm size as moderation

The influence of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds on Wadiah Giro savings which is moderated by company size has been explored in several studies. Muzakir & Dharma (2020b) found that Wadiah Current Accounts and Wadiah Savings had a significant effect on net profit at PT. BRI Syariah Bank. Amalia & Hidayah

(2018) also noted the positive influence of Third Party Funds (DPK) and Return on Assets (ROA) on murabahah financing. Prayogo (2022) further supports the positive influence of the Zakat Performance Ratio (ZPR) on financial performance in Islamic commercial banks, with company size moderating this influence. Maudi et al., (2020) found that corporate social responsibility (CSR) and zakat have a significant influence on profitability, with company size moderating the relationship between CSR and profitability. These studies collectively show that ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds, particularly through Wadiah Giro savings, can have a positive impact on financial performance, with company size playing a moderating role

The influence of FDR on Wadiah Current Account Savings with firm size as moderation
The effect of FDR on Wadiah Giro savings which is moderated by company size has been explored in several studies. Siregar et al., (2023) found that company size moderates the relationship between dividend policy, capital structure, and profitability on company value in the consumer goods sector. Wasista & Asmara Putra (2019) also reported a positive impact of company size on company value, where good corporate governance will strengthen the influence of profitability and company size. Septyaningsih & Risman (2021) found that company size does not moderate the relationship between profitability and free cash flow on the capital structure of the food and beverage subsector. However, Dalci et al., (2019) it shows that firm size moderates the relationship between working capital management and profitability, with smaller firms gaining greater profits by reducing the length of the cash conversion cycle. These studies collectively show that firm size can significantly moderate the relationship between various financial factors and firm value.

The influence of CAR on Wadiah Current Account Savings with firm size as moderation
Pravasanti & Utami (2020) found that wadi'ah demand deposits and savings have a significant effect on bank profitability, while mudharabah savings do not. This shows that the type of savings has a varying impact on profitability. Dwi Pratomo & Sudjono (2021) further explored the influence of profitability, corporate social responsibility, and firm size on company value, finding that profitability had a positive and significant effect, while company size (firm size) had a negative and insignificant effect. Ahmed Hashed Abdullah (2021) also noted a positive relationship between company size and profitability, indicating that larger companies are more profitable. Atiningsih & Setiyono (2023) adding that company size can moderate the influence of eco-efficiency on company value. These studies collectively show that wadi'ah giro savings, profitability, and company size are important factors in the financial performance of Islamic banks.

The Effect of Receipt of ZISWAF, FDR and CAR Funds on Wadiah Current Account Savings

The influence of ZISWAF, FDR, and CAR funds on Giro Wadiah savings are factors that influence each other and are complex. Muzakir & Dharma (2020a) found that Wadi'ah Giro and Wadi'ah Savings had a significant influence on net profit at PT. BRI Syariah Bank. Further Amalia & Hidayah (2018) supporting this, it shows that Third Party Funds (DPK) and Return on Assets (ROA) have a positive effect on murabahah financing. However, Iswanto (2023) we Yulyani et al., (2021) found that CAR and FDR did not have a significant effect on murabahah financing, but were moderated by Non-Performing

Financing (NPF). These studies collectively show that although ZISWAF, FDR, and CAR funds may have an influence on Wadiah Giro savings, their impact is most likely mediated by other factors such as NPF.

CONCLUSION

Based on the test results, it can be concluded that the receipt of ZISWAF (Zakah, Infaq, Sadaqah, & Waqf) Funds has a significant negative effect on Wadiah Current Account Savings. This shows that the higher the ZISWAF fund receipts received, the higher the Wadiah Giro Savings will be, and vice versa. FDR shows a significant negative influence on Wadiah Current Account Savings. If the resulting FDR is high it will result in a decrease in Wadiah Giro Savings, and vice versa. CAR shows a significant positive influence on Wadiah Giro Savings. If the resulting CAR is high it will cause Wadiah Current Account Savings to increase, and vice versa. Then, in the interaction of the moderating variables, firm size (company size) cannot moderate the influence of ZISWAF and FDR fund receipts on Wadiah Current Account Savings in the financial sector in the 2018-2023 period. However, firm size can moderate the influence of CAR on Gross NPF in the financial sector in the 2018-2023 period.

SUGGESTION

In future research, it is hoped that other variables will be used as variables that can become moderating variables. Apart from that, in future research it is recommended not only to look at companies from the financial sector, but also to look at companies from other sectors so that the research results can also represent other business sectors.

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